

NON-FARM INCOME DIVERSIFICATION AND POVERTY REDUCTION IN NIGERIA: A
PROPENSITY-SCORE MATCHING ANALYSISOlugbire, O.O¹., Falusi², A.O., Adeoti², A.I., Oyekale² A.S., and Adeniran¹ O.A.,¹Department of Forest Economics and Extension, Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, ²Department of Agricultural Economics, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we investigate the impact of non-farm employment (disaggregated by wage- and self-employment) on household income and poverty. Using a propensity score matching model, we evaluate the differences in outcomes between households who participate in the non-farm employment and those who do not. The results from the study show that non-farm wage-employed households in rural Nigeria have a significantly higher income than self-employed households. Second, we show that non-farm wage-employment impacts more on household welfare than non-farm self-employment. Third, we show that the benefits to non-farm wage-employment are much higher among the non-poor than among the poor.

KEYWORDS: Non-farm employment; Poverty; Matching

Introduction

In developing countries such as Nigeria, poverty and income variability remains a formidable challenge for several rural households. The strategies households in these areas often use to strengthen income have been a topic for research in recent times (Reardon *et al.*; 1992; Ellis, 2000). Studies on rural income growth suggests that diversification of income sources is a key strategy individuals and households use to strengthen their income sources and thus reduce poverty (Illiya, 1999; Minot *et al.* 2006).

Nigeria as a nation has great potential for development in terms of human, material and natural resources. It has a population of 150 million – the largest in Africa – and a fast-growing economy (IFAD 2010). Agriculture is the mainstay of the economy, contributing about 45 per cent of GDP. According to IDEA (2011), the agriculture sector employs about two-thirds of the country's total labour force and provides a livelihood for about 90 per cent of the rural population. Nigeria is the world's largest producer of cassava, yam and cowpea – all staple foods in sub-Saharan Africa. It is also a major producer of fish. Yet it is a food-deficit nation and imports large amounts of grain, livestock products and fish (IFAD 2010). Nigeria's huge agricultural resource base offers great potential for growth. The great diversity of the country's agro-ecological zones and mineral resources offers a challenging environment in which poverty-focused programmes could succeed. However, despite Nigeria's diverse resources and oil wealth, poverty is widespread in the country and has increased since the late 1990s. According to Vision 2020:20 document, about 70 per cent of Nigerians are now classified as poor, and that the rural sector has been facing a relatively more serious poverty situation than the urban. The document also highlights that poverty is particularly a serious challenge in Nigeria and poverty reduction is the most difficult challenge facing Nigeria and its people, and the greatest obstacle to pursuit of sustainable socio-economic growth.

Poverty reduction has therefore being on the agenda of international development agencies as well as governmental and non-governmental organizations. Several potential exit paths out of rural poverty have been suggested in the literature (De Janvry *et al.*, 2005). In the poverty reduction strategy report by the government of Nigeria, a new approach to poverty reduction that takes a comprehensive view of the multiplicity of income sources that rural household will rely upon has been developed. An important aspect of this new approach is the promotion of rural non-farm activities (other wise known as non-farm income diversification) and enhancing access of the rural households to these sources of income.

In many countries including Nigeria, income diversification strategies by rural households is not new and most of these families have truly multiple income sources. This may indeed include; off-farm wage work in

agriculture, but is also likely to involve wage work in non-farm activities, rural non-farm self- and wage-employments (Awoyemi 2011; Escobal 2001; Scwarze 2004).

This study is stimulated by this preliminary insight that rural households do not depend on farming as the only source of income, but on a variety of non-farm income sources. The nature of these incomes and their effect on welfare among rural households need to be better understood for priority setting. Since the goal of any poverty reduction strategy is to increase income and other welfare indicators of rural households (Gordon and Craig, 2004), any policy which aim is to increase income should first understand the composition of these income sources, so that target interventions can be applied appropriately. Here, we analyse the various activities rural households engage to generate income, the share income from each activity and its effect on household welfare. The results of the findings would help in drawing policy conclusions with respect to rural poverty reduction and rural development. The rest of the article proceeds as follows: section 2 describes the data used and methodology implemented, section 3 presents the main results on income generating activities and the propensity score matching estimates, section 4 draws out the main conclusions.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

Data Source and Scope

The data used for the study were collected by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). They were based on the Nigeria Living Standards Surveys (NLSS) of households that was carried out between September 2003 and August 2004. The questionnaire development was a joint effort of the Nigerian Bureau of Statistics, the World Bank and the National Planning Commission. The survey covered the rural areas of the 36 states of the Federation and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). Ten Enumeration Areas were studied in each of the states while five were covered in Abuja. In-depth data were collected on key elements which includes demographic characteristics, educational skills and training, employment and time use, social capital, agriculture, income, consumption expenditure and non-farm enterprises. The NLSS sample design was two-stage stratified. The first stage was the cluster of housing units called Enumeration Areas (EAs), while the second stage was the housing units. One and twenty EAs were selected in each state while sixty were selected in the FCT. Five housing units were selected in each of the selected EAs. Fifty housing units were covered in each state and twenty five housing units in the FCT per month. Each state had a sample size of 600 housing units, while the FCT had a sample size of 300. The national sample size for the 12-month survey period was 21,900 housing units. However, some households did not fully complete the questionnaires. Out of 21,900 households that were targeted for the survey, only 19,158 completed the survey. Although there are 19,158 urban and rural households in the full sample, the analysis focused on rural households, which total 14,512. The following household incomes were identified based on their sources: Income earned from cropping and livestock activities; Income earned from self-employment in non-farm activities such as industry, transportation, construction and services; Income earned from formal or informal wage, including salary, allowance, bonus, and other kinds of remuneration, and other non-productive incomes, such as remittances, transfers, rents and financial income. Non-farm activities were further categorised into self-employment and wage employment.

Analytical Techniques: Propensity Score Matching Approach

Estimation strategy

The estimation strategy follows Pham (2006) and Khan (2008):

Let Y_{i1} represents the expenditure level of the i^{th} diversified household (also called the treatment) and Y_{i0} represents the expenditure level of households who did not participate in non-farm activities (also called the control).

Let D_i be a treatment indicator which is a binary variable, coded as one if a household is participating in non-farm activities and zero otherwise. Then the observed welfare outcome of the i^{th} household is: $Y_i = D_i Y_{i1} + (1 - D_i) Y_{i0}$ and the welfare effect of being diversified for a single household is $\tau_i = Y_{i1} - Y_{i0}$.

The welfare effect of non-farm diversification can be estimated through matching the diversified households with the undiversified counterparts. Effectively, it implies assigning observations into cells defined by unique values of the covariates. However, this matching is difficult when the vector is highly dimensional, and especially when it includes some continuous variables. In this Rosenbaum and Rubin (1983) develop a proposition which allows the use of propensity score, defined as the conditional probability of receiving a

treatment (that is being diversified in this case) given a set of covariates, to reduce the dimensionality of this matching.

The propensity score of i^{th} household to diversify is defined as:

$$p(T_i) \equiv \Pr(D_i = 1|T_i) = E(D_i|T_i) \quad (1)$$

Where $p(T_i)$ = the conditional probability of the i^{th} household being diversified into nonfarm activities.

Rosenbaum and Rubin (1983) argue that if there are no systematic pre-treatment differences between the treatment and the control groups, conditional to the observable T_i , there would also be no systematic pre-treatment differences between the treatment and the control, conditional to the propensity score, $p(T_i)$. In other words, conditional to the $p(T_i)$, Y_{i1} or Y_{i0} are orthogonal to the treatment indicator D_i with all i .

Following Rosenbaum and Rubin's (1983) proposition, the ATT can be given as:

$$\tau|_{D_i=1} = E\{E(Y_i|p(T_i), D_i = 1) - E(Y_i|p(T_i), D_i = 0)|D_i = 1\} \quad (2)$$

According to Pham (2006), moving from (1) to (2) means a move from estimating the Average Treatment effects on the Treated (ATT) conditional to the pre-treatment observable characteristics T_i , to deriving the ATT conditional to a single propensity score index, $p(T_i)$.

In this study, the estimation strategy was carried out in three steps. The first step involved estimating the probability of participating in the non-farm activities conditional on the pre-treatment characteristics, in order to obtain a single index variable, the propensity score, to make the matching feasible. The propensity scores were estimated using the probit model. Next the diversified and undiversified households was matched based on the estimated propensity scores. The matching was carried out using the kernel-based matching method (also known as kernel-based matching algorithm).

Finally, the mean difference in outcomes between the matched treated and the control groups were calculated to obtain the average treatment effect on the treated (ATT) which is the parameter of interest in this study.

Empirical results

Descriptive Analysis of Income and Activities

Results from Table 1 shows that agriculture is the predominant activity among rural dwellers in the study area; about 78 percent of the surveyed households are involved in this activity. The proportion of income generated from this activity by the rural households is small (24.3 percent).

Non-farm activities were categorised into non-farm wage- and self- employment activities. In table 2, it is shown that 15.2 percent and 19.7 percent of the households are engaged in non-farm wage and self employment activities. The share of income from non-farm wage employment is 43.0 percent, while non-farm self employment income share is 23.7 percent. This result shows that, though the percentage of households who are engaged in non-farm wage employment is lower than other activities in the study area, in terms of returns, it is the most remunerative activity in the study area.

Households belonging to the first and the third terciles (Table 3) had slightly higher proportions of non-farm wage employment income (50.0 percent and 49.7 percent), than those in the second tercile. Although the mean income for the poor households is the least, their proportion of income from farm activities is the highest of the three expenditure categories. In terms of participation, participation in agricultural activities is comparatively low for households that are better off (74.3 percent), whereas it is the other way round for non-farm activities. 19.2 percent of the richer households participate in non-farm wage employment while 22.7 percent of the same households participate in non-farm self employment activities. Only 9.6 percent of the poorest households are engaged in non-farm wage employment activities and 17.7 percent participate in non-farm self employment activities.

Male headed households generate 28.1 percent of their income from farm activities; 49.7 percent and 27.6 percent from non-farm wage and self employment activities (Table 4). While female headed households generate 22.2 percent of their income from farm activities; 44.3 percent and 28.1 percent from non-farm wage- and self-employment activities respectively. Participation in farm and non-farm wage employment activities is slightly higher for male headed households, whereas it is the other way round for non-farm self employment activities. 21.6 percent of the female headed households are engaged in non-farm self employment activities while 19.2 percent of the male headed households are engaged in the same activities.

Table 1 Composition of Household Income by Sector

Sector	Share in total income (%)	No of households	% of households
Agriculture	24.3	10212	78.35
Professional/technical	14.4	651	5.00
Administration	6.2	14	0.11
Clerical	7.3	428	3.28
Sales and related	8.5	793	6.08
Services and related	7.7	319	2.45
Production and transport	11.2	202	1.55
Manufacturing and processing	11.1	122	0.94
Other	9.3	292	2.24
Total	100	13033	100

Source: calculations using data from Nigeria Living Standards Survey (2004)

Table 2 Composition of household income by activity

Income activity	Share in total income (%)	No of households participating	% of households
Farm activity	24.3	10212	78.4
Nonfarm wage employment	43.0	1975	15.2
Nonfarm self employment	23.7	2568	19.7
Other			
Remittances	5.9	1451	11.1
Transfers	3.0	3800	29.1

Source: calculations using data from Nigeria Living Standards Survey (2004)

Table 3 Composition of Household Income by Poverty Group (Expenditure Tercile)

Expenditure Tercile	First	Second	Third
Farm income			
Shares in total income (%)	25.8	24.2	21.7
No of households participating	2970	3754	3838
% of households participating	87.8	83.7	74.3
Nonfarm wage income			
Shares in total income (%)	50.6	47.6	49.7
No of households participating	323	661	991
% of households participating	9.6	14.7	19.2
Nonfarm self employment Income			
Shares in total income (%)	23.6	28.2	28.6
No of households participating	598	798	1172
% of households participating	17.7	17.8	22.7

Source: calculations using data from Nigeria Living Standards Survey (2004)

Table 4 Composition of Household Income by Gender of the Household Head

	Male	Female
Farm income		
Shares in total income (%)	28.1	22.2
No of households participating	8251	2311
% of households participating	81.1	18.9
Nonfarm wage income		
Shares in total income (%)	49.7	44.3
No of households participating	1739	236
% of households participating	17.1	8.3
Nonfarm self employment Income		
Shares in total income (%)	27.6	28.1
No of households participating	1950	618
% of households participating	19.2	21.6

Source: calculations using data from Nigeria Living Standards Survey (2004)

Estimates of the Propensity Score Matching results of the impact of nonfarm income on household welfare. Two matching algorithms were used for the matching and for every matching algorithm; the ATT is positive which means that income diversification account for a positive and statistically significant difference in per capita expenditures between diversified households and non-diversified households (Tables 5 and 6). The results from table 5 show that, households with non-farm wage- and self-employment have higher consumption expenditures than households engaged in farming only. Households engaged in non-farm wage-employment have average consumption expenditures of 7337.76 naira more than a similar household that is

engaged only in farming activities. While households engaged in non-farm self-employment have average consumption expenditures of 3389.73 naira higher than similar household that is engaged in farming alone. Outcome difference between non-farm wage-and self-employment shows that non-farm wage-employment impacts more on household welfare than non-farm self-employment.

The result of the average of the pair wise difference between the poor and the non-poor households in Table 6 revealed that difference in consumption expenditures between the non-farm wage- and self-employed and farm workers is much smaller among the poor than among the non-poor. This implies that the welfare outcome is more pronounced among the non-poor than the poor. A poor household with non-farm wage-employment has average consumption expenditures of 1215.29 naira more than similar poor household engaged in farming activities alone. Also a poor household with non-farm wage-employment has average consumption expenditures of 2821.49 naira less than a similar poor household with non-farm self-employment activities. This implies that poor household that diversifies into non-farm self-employment is likely to have an improved welfare than diversifying into non-farm wage employment.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated non-farm income diversification and its impact on household welfare in rural Nigeria, using nationally representative data. A propensity score matching model was employed to estimate the impact of participating in non-farm activities on household welfare. The paper provides separate estimates for the impacts of self-employment and wage-employment as well as for poor and the non-poor. The results of the descriptive analysis show that income from non-farm sources takes a higher share in household income, therefore non-farm activity can no longer be considered as residual by households in rural Nigeria and should be given considerations in any rural development initiatives. The results of the impacts of non-farm income on household welfare show that non-farm income has a positive and robust effect on household consumption expenditure and could be a way out of poverty for rural households. This implies that non-farm income diversification significantly improves household consumption expenditure. The results also show that non-farm wage-employment produced higher welfare impact compared with non-farm self-employment. Self-employment was found to have a positive and significant impact on consumption expenditures for the poor.

Based on the above findings we suggest that policy measures which aims at poverty reduction could target the rural poor to improve their participation in non-farm self-employment. Such measures include access to assets such as financial capital, improved infrastructures and training. These assets according to Owusu and Abdulai (2009) can help them overcome the entry barriers to non-farm employment, particularly non-farm self-employment.

Table 5: Estimates of Differences in Per Capita Expenditure by Activity

Outcome: Per Capita Expenditure – All Households							
		Kernel matching			Radius matching		
		ATT	Standard Error	t-value	ATT	Standard Error	t-value
Nonfarm employment versus farming	wage-	7337.76	702.41	9.66***	7313.72	700.48	9.42***
Nonfarm employment versus farming	self-	3389.73	786.27	4.57***	3925.95	865.53	4.77***
Nonfarm employment versus nonfarm self-employment	wage-	7112.24	217.43	5.12***	7334.11	279.58	5.95***
	self-						

Source: computations from the Nigeria Living Standards Survey (2004)

Note: *** indicates significance at the 1% level, ATT = Average Treatment effects on the Treated

Table 6: Estimates of Differences in Per Capita Expenditure by Poverty Status

Outcome: Per Capita Expenditure – Poverty Status							
Poor		Kernel matching			Radius matching		
		ATT	Standard Error	t-value	ATT	Standard Error	t-value
Nonfarm employment farming	wage-versus	1215.29	308.39	2.10**	1402.07	511.64	2.74**
Nonfarm employment farming	self-versus	523.27	158.33	5.30***	672.13	613.27	5.60***
Nonfarm employment nonfarm employment	wage-versus self-employment	-2821.49	206.33	-13.67***	-3626.97	406.86	-14.91***
Non poor		Kernel matching			Radius matching		
		ATT	Standard Error	t-value	ATT	Standard Error	t-value
Nonfarm employment farming	wage-versus	5130.46	2214.11	2.32**	7348.96	3635.24	4.77***
Nonfarm employment farming	self-versus	2630.93	1549.56	1.70*	1056.55	1376.31	1.34
Nonfarm employment nonfarm employment	wage-versus self-employment	-1199.24	2565.93	-0.47	-1172.26	1438.40	-0.96

Source: Computations from the Nigeria Living Standards Survey (2004)

Note: *** indicates significance at the 1% level, ** at the 5% level, and * at the 10 % level

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